

resulting solid was purified by washing successively with boiling ethanol and hot dimethylformamide (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Yield %
3a	H	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	288	44
3b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	272	32
3c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	271	31
3d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	279	56
3e	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	274	27.7
3f	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	258	44.4
3g	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	241	46.8
3h	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	274	14.6
3i	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	265	18.6
3j	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	262	27.9
4a	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃	245	38.56
4b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	250d	37.22
4c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	260d	29.77
4d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	265	29.77
4e	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄	248	50.11
4f	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	255	28.36
4g	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	261	23.64
4h	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	225	30.76

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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Synthesis of some New 4-Hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones and their Triazolo Derivatives as Possible Antibacterial Agents

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It has been reported that some fused triazoles of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones possess promising pharmacological properties¹. The presence of halogen

atoms in benzene ring of benzoxazine molecule imparts marked antibacterial activity to 4-*N*-dialkylhydrazido derivatives^{2,3}. On the basis of these observations the synthesis of 4-hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones (3a-h)² was undertaken. On cyclodehydration with ammonium acetate and acetic acid these were converted to 5-oxo-1,2,4-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-2(H), 3(H)-1,4-benzoxazines 4 (Scheme 1).

- (a), R=R''=Br, R'=H (e), R=Br, R'=H, R''=CH₃
 (b), R=Br, R'=H, R''=Cl (f), R=R''=Br, R'=CH₃
 (c), R=Cl, R'=H, R''=Br (g), R=CH₃, R'=H, R''=Br
 (d); R=R''=CH₃, R'=H (h), R=Cl, R'=CH₃, R''=Br

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) Cl-COOC₂H₅/K₂CO₃/CH₃OH,
 (ii) N₂H₄·H₂O/C₂H₅OH, (iii) CH₃COOH/
 CH₃COONH₄.

All these compounds (3 and 4) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus aureus*, *Esch. coli* and *Salmonella typhosa* by the cup-plate method⁴ at concentration of 1 mg ml⁻¹ in acetone.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. 1,4-Benzoxazin-3(2H)-ones (1a-h) were prepared by the known procedure². For compounds 2-4, b and c have same not formulae, which is also true for the pair e and g. Elemental analysis for C, H and N, were found satisfactory for all compounds.

Preparation of 2a-h: A mixture of 1e (0.03 mol), ethyl chloroformate (0.07 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.0 g) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was triturated with water to remove K₂CO₃, filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give 2e (83%), m.p. 78° (Found: C, 45.80; H, 3.80; N, 4.40. C₁₂H₁₂O₄NBr requires: C, 46.01; H, 3.83; N, 4.47%); ν_{max} 1740 (C=O, ester), 1670 (C=O, δ-lactam) and 1320 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 1.3 (3H, t, J 7Hz, CH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, J 7Hz, CH₂), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂) and 6.6-7.5 (2H,

m, ArH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%) and m.p., (°C) are: **2a**, $C_{11}H_9NO_4Br_2$, 76, 64; **2b**, $C_{11}H_9NO_4BrCl$, 87, 54; **2c**, 76, 58; **2d**, $C_{13}H_{15}NO_4$, 79, 44; **2f**, $C_{12}H_{11}NO_4Br_2$, 88, 62; **2g**, 78, b.p. 290°; **2h**, $C_{12}H_{11}NO_4BrCl$, 87, 62.

Preparation of 3a-h: A mixture of **2b** (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.056 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. On cooling white needle shaped crystals that separated were recrystallised from ethanol to give **3b**, (75%), m.p. 131° (Found: C, 33.60; H, 2.10; N, 13.05. $C_9H_7O_3N_3BrCl$ requires: C, 33.80; H, 2.19; N, 13.15%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NHNH₂) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (CO-NH); δ 2.5 (2H, br s, NH₂), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.0–7.5 (2H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, br s, NH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%), m.p. (°C) are: **3a**, $C_9H_7N_3O_3Br_2$, 78, 224; **3c**, 77, 112; **3d**, $C_{11}H_{13}N_3O_3$, 73, 82; **3e**, $C_{10}H_{10}N_3O_3Br$, 80, 171; **3f**, $C_{10}H_9N_3O_3Br_2$, 70, 84; **3g**, 78, 78; **3h**, $C_{10}H_9N_3O_3BrCl$, 76, 187.

Preparation of 4: A mixture of compound **3g** (0.001 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for **4h**, when the yellow colour of reaction mixture changed to dark brown. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to yield **4a**, (68%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 31.20; H, 1.30; N, 12.00. $C_9H_7O_3N_3Br_2$ requires: C, 31.30; H, 1.45; N, 12.17%); ν_{max} 3 480–3 200 (NH), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 5.1 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.2–7.5 (2H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, br s, NH). For other compounds, mol. formulae, yield (%), m.p. (°C) are: **4b**, $C_9H_7N_3O_2BrCl$, 72, 212; **4c**, 63, 118; **4e**, $C_{10}H_8N_3O_2Br$, 66, 114; **4g**, 75, 96; **4h**, $C_{10}H_7N_3O_2BrCl$, 65, 110.

Antibacterial activity: The results of antibacterial screening indicated that good activity was shown by **3b, c, h** against *S. aureus*, by **3b, c** against *S. aureus* and by **4b, c** against *E. coli*; these compounds also showed moderate activity against *S. typhosa*. All other compounds showed moderate, weak or no activity against the bacterial strains. Two generalisations can be made from these results. Firstly, in comparison with **3a-h**, triazoles **4a-c, e, g, h** were found to be marginally less active and secondly, compounds **3** and **4** with the substitution pattern R/R' = Cl/Br, R'' = H appear to be more active than otherwise substituted compounds.

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Synthesis of some Substituted 2-Azetidinone and 4-Thiazolidinones

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EARLIER we reported the synthesis and biological activities of various hydrazino derivatives of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one¹. Since the β -lactam ring is responsible for the activity of the β -lactam antibiotics whose reactivity is greatly influenced by substituents or fused rings² and since the incorporation of azetidinone or thiazolidinone moiety enhances the biological activity³, we have reported herein the synthesis of various 1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-diones bearing 2-azetidinone and 4-thiazolidinone moieties.

The starting compound 1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione was prepared by the method described in literature⁴. This on refluxing with ethyl chloroformate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave the 4-carbomethoxy derivative (**1**). On being refluxed with ethanolic hydrazine hydrate, **1** gave the *N*-hydrazides (**2**), which on condensation with various substituted aldehydes produced the Schiff bases (**3**)⁵.

The compounds **3** on condensation with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine produced the corresponding 2-azetidinones (**4**). This cyclocondensation proceeds via ketene intermediate⁶. The action of mercaptoacetic acid on the Schiff bases (**3**) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride yielded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (**5**).

The compounds have been characterised by ir and nmr data.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

4-Hydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione (2): A solution of **1** (0.1 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h, then excess ethanol removed and the concentrate kept overnight. The resulting crystals were dried and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless